

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE SPIRITUAL HERITAGE OF THE UZBEK PEOPLE IN THE FORMATION OF MUSICAL CULTURE AMONG STUDENTS OF PEDAGOGICAL UNIVERSITIES OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article examines the importance of the spiritual heritage of the Uzbek people in the formation of musical culture among students of pedagogical universities of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: musical theoretical thought in Central Asia, opera, symphony, ballet.

Introduction.

The President of our country, Sh. M. Mirziyoyev, in September 2020, at a ceremony dedicated to the 29th anniversary of independence, announced the beginning of the Third Renaissance, calling culture and education the main pillar on which the new Uzbekistan is being built. National culture and science, which have a long history, became a solid foundation for the Third Renaissance. The ideas of reviving the creativity of outstanding cultural figures, learned encyclopedists, distinguished by high spirituality, a sense of national pride and unique universal qualities, have deep meaning for modern Uzbekistan at the moment.

The study of the best examples of Uzbek and world literature and culture is carried out at the Faculty of “Musical Culture” at the Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami in the course “History of Music”, which consists of three sections: “History of Foreign Music”, “History of Russian Music” and “History Uzbek music”. Each of these sections considers the art of music as a continuously developing social and historical process, in all its diversity of connections and phenomena.

The course “History of Uzbek Music” is studied by students in two stages. In bachelor's and master's degrees.

At the undergraduate level, this subject provides students with knowledge of Uzbek musical culture on topics relevant to the course program.

The focus of the program on developing key knowledge among students poses new methodological challenges for the discipline. The most important of them is the achievement of such a quality of knowledge that allows us to understand this subject as a holistically developing world, connected with the entire spiritual and material culture of the Uzbek people. This quality is associated with the systematic nature of knowledge.

The methodological basis for the formation of knowledge on the history of Uzbek musical culture is the historical aspect, the significance of which lies in the fact that each musical phenomenon is assessed against the background of the historical process, it is correlated with similar phenomena of other eras, its connection with the past and direction to the future is comprehended.

Musical art is considered as a continuously developing social and historical process, in all the diversity of connections and phenomena (Ancient musical culture of Central Asia; Art of the early Middle Ages (IV-IX centuries); Musical life in the Samanid state (IX-X centuries); Musical culture during education of the Uzbek people (XI-XV centuries); Musical culture of the 16th - 19th centuries; Musical culture of the late 19th - early 20th centuries; Modern Uzbek music.).

Much attention in the course "History of Uzbek Music" is paid to familiarization with the most important philosophical and aesthetic teachings that have become the basis of musical theoretical thought in Central Asia. We highlight the activities of al-Farabi, who connected the science of the East with antiquity, with the science of Ancient Greece. He became famous as a commentator on Aristotle, for which he received the honorary name of "second teacher." Al-Farabi made a great contribution to music theory. While studying acoustics, he used the scale of the lute (ud) to calculate the intervals of the scale.

Another outstanding scientist of the East, Ibn Sino, in his works provides information about music, its physical properties, musical modes and rhythmic basis. In the Book of Healing and the Book of Salvation, Ibn Sina develops the acoustic side of musical science.

We note the significance of the "Treatise on Music" by Abdurrahman Jami (1414-1492), who continued and developed the basic musical theoretical principles of his predecessors, al-Farabi, Ibn Sina, Abd al-Qadir. Like them, Jami gives intervallic relationships of tones, deducing them from the ratio of parts of the strings, shows the method of formation of the main scales (tetrachord and pentachord) and the method of forming modes from them.

The course "History of Uzbek Music" is aimed at developing broad, versatile knowledge about the history of Uzbekistan, literature, poetry and painting.

Thus, when studying opera, students get acquainted with the authentic historical events that took place in ancient Sogdiana in the 4th century, before. e. (334), when the Sogdian lands were captured by Alexander the Great, during the time of Spitamen (opera “The Leopard from Sogdiana” by I. Akbarov), with great historical heroes - Ulugbek (opera of the same name by A. Kozlovsky, “Samarkand Legend” by G. Mushel) , Timur Malik (symphonic poem by M. Ashrafi), etc.

The impetus for the creative imagination of many Uzbek composers was the ancient monuments of architecture, which was reflected in the names of the parts: “Bibi-khanym”, “Registan”, “Ulugbek Madrasah”, “Shah-i Zinda”, “Gur Emir” in (“Samarkand stories”) by I. Akbarov (1972), dedicated to the 2500th anniversary of Samarkand and, naturally, connected in design with its historical past.

Getting acquainted with musical and stage works, students will learn the works of Navoi, which became the plots of the opera “Leyla and Majnun” by R. Gliere and T. Sadykov, a one-act ballet on the same plot by Ikram Akbarov, the opera “Dilarom” by M. Ashrafi (based on one of the parts Alisher Navoi's poem “Seven Planets”), “Farhad and Shirin” by V. Uspensky and G. Mushel, etc. The poem by H. Alimdzhan became the plot of the opera “Zainab and Amon” by T. Sadykov and B. Zeidman, the work of Turab Tula - the opera “Light from darkness” by R. Khamraev, etc.

All the main material for the course “History of Uzbek Music” is structured according to the genre principle, and this allows our students to clearly understand the change in artistic and stylistic eras and the evolution of the most important genres. These are the topics: vocal, instrumental music, opera, ballet, symphonic music.

Since the course “History of Uzbek Music” is structured problematically, the actual analysis of musical works has a subordinate importance here, being either the preparation of musical historical generalizations, or their specification, however, students have the opportunity to clearly understand the evolution of the most important genres and forms in the work of Uzbek composers .

It is known that the Uzbek musical culture of the 20th century was enriched with new genres, which include both traditional Eastern and traditional Western forms. Getting acquainted with the topic “Symphonic music”, students have the opportunity to learn that in the works of composers such as M. Bafoev, new genre types have appeared that cannot be reduced to either European or Eastern models. These are works with double genre designations, such as

“symphony-ghazal” (for soloist, male choir, strings and percussion by M. Bafoev), “symphony-ballet” by M. Tadzhev (second program symphony “Oygul and Bakhtiyor” by fairy tale by X. Alimdzhah).

Studying modern Uzbek music, students become familiar with such concepts as maqom symphonism, presented in the work of M. Tadzhev, who in his best symphonies (First, Third, Fifth, Ninth) interprets the symphony genre based on the musical patterns of maqoms.

By forming musical, historical and theoretical knowledge in the course “History of Uzbek Music,” we set ourselves a specific goal: to teach students to comprehend each musical phenomenon from the standpoint of general cultural and historical processes, to analyze musical works and have an idea about their dramaturgy, to identify characteristic features style of a particular composer, creative direction. Students should be able to reveal how the ideas of time are embodied in specific musical phenomena, and how a given musical phenomenon is assessed against the background of a certain historical process as a whole. As a result, such personality qualities as creativity, independence, cognitive interest, competence, professionalism and musical culture are formed.

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